

triazine: 2-(2'-Methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-chloro-*s*-triazine (0.01 mol) and various phenylureas (0.01 mol) in acetone or dioxane were refluxed for 3 h on a water-bath keeping pH of the solution at 7 by adding aqueous 2% NaOH. The resulting clear solution was added in crushed ice, filtered and recrystallised from ethanol. The yield of the compounds varied from 69 to 82%, m p. R = phenyl, 167°; *o*-tolyl, 156°; *m*-tolyl, 172°; *p*-tolyl, 180°; *o*-nitrophenyl 169°; *m* nitrophenyl 186°; *p*-nitrophenyl, 154°; *o*-chlorophenyl, 135°; *m*-chlorophenyl, 128°; *p*-chlorophenyl, 140°.

Ir spectra (KBr) recorded on a Parkin-Elmer spectrophotometer revealed the following bands for all compounds in general: 1 540-1 510 (NH bend), 1 660-1 600 (C-O stretch), 1 240-1 200 (C-O-C stretch) and 870-850 cm^{-1} (C_3N_3 stretch).

Antibacterial activity: The purified product was screened for antibacterial activity by cup-plate method using a species of gram-positive bacteria (*S. aureus*) and a species of gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*). Testing was carried out in ethanol solution at a concentration of 10 mg ml^{-1} . The zone of inhibition of the test solutions were recorded.

The zone of inhibition was found considerable against *S. aureus*, for 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-(phenylureido)-*s*-triazine and 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-(3'-methylphenylureido)-*s*-triazine as 2.5 and 2.0 mm, respectively. While the marked zone of inhibition was obtained against *E. coli*, for 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-(3'-methylphenylureido)-*s*-triazine and 2-(2'-methoxyanilino)-4-(benzamido-2'-yl-oxo)-6-(2'-nitrophenylureido)-*s*-triazine as 2.0 and 1.0 mm, respectively.

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Olean-12-ene-28-oic-3-O- β -D-glucopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)-O- α -L-xylopyranoside from *Gardenia latifolia* Ait. Stems

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GARDENIA latifolia (Ait.)¹ N.O. Rubiaceae is known as 'Papra' in Hindi and found throughout the greater parts of India. Earlier workers have already reported the presence of episiaeresinolic acid and D-mannitol, sitosterol, oleanolic acid, siarsinolic, spinosis acid and hederagenin from the bark and stem bark respectively^{2,3}.

The methanol soluble part of the rectified spirit extract of the stem yielded a saponin, which was found to be homogeneous on tlc and analysed for $\text{C}_{41}\text{H}_{66}\text{O}_{13}$, m p. 218°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 16.8^\circ$ (in pyridine), $M^+ 750$. It responded to all the characteristic reactions of saponin⁴⁻⁶. On acid hydrolysis it yielded sapogenin and sugars identified as D-glucose and L-xylose (by co-pc and tlc). The sapogenin analysed for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_8$, m p. 307° $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 78.5^\circ$ (in CHCl_3), $M^+ 456$. It gave all the colour reactions characteristic of pentacyclic triterpene. It formed a monoacetyl derivative ($\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_4$, m.p. 269°) with Ac_2O /pyridine, confirming the presence of one OH group. It was identified as oleanolic acid by co-pc, tlc and m.m p.; ν_{max} (KBr) 3 420, 3 030, 2 900, 1 667, 1 391, 1 381, 1 370, 1 360, 1 346, 1 295, 810 and 800 cm^{-1} ; δ 0.95, 0.97, 0.82, 0.89, 1.10, 1.26-2.00, 2.03, 3.2, 5.50, 2.50, 4.29, 5.47, 3.40-4.18, 2.06, 2.08, 2.00, 2.15, 2.18 and 2.22; m/e 415, 441, 411, 410, 395, 248, 207, 203, 189, 175 and 133. Positive Zimmermann test while indicated the presence of C_3 -OH. On partial hydrolysis with 0.02 N H_2SO_4 it showed the appearance of D-glucose first followed by L-xylose thereby showing D-glucose to be terminal sugar.

The saponin on permethylation by Kuhn⁸ procedure yielded 2,3 di-O-methylxylose and 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose. Periodate⁹ oxidation and per-methylation followed by hydrolysis confirmed that both the sugars were present in pyranose form. Enzymatic¹⁰ hydrolysis with enzyme emulsion revealed β -linkage between L-xylose and D glucose and α -linkage between sapogenin and L-xylose. Specific rotation measurements confirmed that glucose was present in D-form and xylose in L-form. Thus the structure of the saponin was assigned as olean-12-ene-28-oic-3-O-D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)-O- α -L-xylopyranoside.

Experimental

The stem (2 kg) of *Gardenia latifolia* (Ait.) collected locally and authenticated by the Botany Department of this University, was air-dried

powdered and extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The defatted stem was extracted with 95% ethanol for 25 days, and the extract (3 dm³) concentrated to a brown viscous mass was treated with methanol. The methanol soluble part was concentrated to a brown viscous mass and excess of solvent ether (250 ml) added to get a precipitate. The precipitate was purified by column chromatography over column silica gel G with acetone–methanol (3 : 1) to yield the saponin, m.p. 218°, which was found to be homogeneous by tlc in BAW (4 : 1 : 5), $R_f=0.69$.

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Chemical Constituents of *Canarium strictum* Gum

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PLANTS of genus *Burseraceae* are well known for their economical and medicinal values¹. *Canarium strictum* gum, commonly known as Kala Dammer,

has been found as a rich source of triterpenoids². Literature review also indicated the presence of canarone apart from other terpenic compounds³.

In our present studies on its gum a new derivative of β -amyrin has been isolated along with four other compounds, which are identified as α -amyrin, β -amyrin, β -amyrin acetate and sitosterol by direct comparison.

Compound-A, m.p. 225°, isolated from petroleum ether extract was analysed for $C_{31}H_{50}O_2$. The ir spectra showed the presence of a C=O group (1720 cm⁻¹). In the ¹H nmr spectral signal for the methine proton was observed at δ 4.48 (t) and the singlet at δ 8.06 is assigned to the formyl proton. Compound-A on alkali hydrolysis afforded a compound-B, m.p. 197°, which showed the presence of OH group in the ir spectra. It was identified as β -amyrin by direct comparison. From the above studies compound-A seems to be the formyl derivative of β -amyrin. The final confirmation of the structure of compound-A was done by preparing the formate of β -amyrin and comparison of both. The mass fragmentation pattern further confirmed the structure which showed a strong $M-CO$ (426) fragment. This is the first report of the occurrence of β -amyrin formate from a natural source.

Experimental

All the m.p.s. were recorded on the Kofler block and are uncorrected. Compounds were separated by column chromatography on silica gel. Ir spectra was recorded on Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian T60A and Jeol/FX-90 spectrometers and mass spectra on a JM5D-300 spectrometer.

The air-dried powder gum (250 g) was extracted in petroleum ether. The concentrated petroleum ether extract was fractionated by column chromatography to collect five compounds. Compound-A as white needles, m.p. 225° (Found : C, 80.09 ; H, 10.9. $C_{31}H_{50}O_2$ requires : C, 81.93 ; H, 11.01%) ; ν_{max} (KBr) 2900, 1720, 1540, 1275, 1200 and 780 cm⁻¹ ; δ (CDCl₃) 8.06 (1H, s, CHO), 5.06 (1H, bs, C₁₃-H), 4.48 (1H, t, J 7Hz, C₈-H), 1.6–1.02 (18H, 3H, bs, 9×CH₂) and 1.02–0.7 (24H, bs, 8×CH₃) ; m/z 454 (M^+) 426, 250, 216 and 207.

Formylation of compound-A : β -Amyrin (50 mg) was dissolved in dry ether (25 ml) and added slowly to the formylating reagent⁴ (10 ml) (prepared by adding 10 ml HCOOH to 20 ml Ac₂O at -5 to 10°) with constant stirring at 10–30°. The reaction mixture was left at the same temperature for 4 h and then poured in ice-water, extracted with CHCl₃ (3×50 ml). The CHCl₃ extract was concentrated to collect the product (40 mg) which was purified by chromatography and identified (compound-A) by m.m.p., co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra.